

Living Gratitude Unfolds the Good That You Desire

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Being grateful has unleashed in me a mind-set that I should give my best and highest in everything I think, feel, say and do in order to unfold the good that I desire easily and effortlessly.

1) THINK

Living gratitude has taught me that I should uphold the highest and best thoughts I can under all circumstances and it will produce the image I want in my mind or something better.

Through the power of meditation, I realized that thoughts really have no power over me. I can consciously think the thoughts I choose to radiate.

By virtue of radiation and attraction, it is within my capacity to overlook present circumstances and think of my life as beautifully as it can be and not just how it appears to be.

Let me give an example, there was an instance in my life when I had to wait for payment to me by my client.

And instead of noticing the lack and being anxious, I used my creative imagination and used my thoughts to imagine money being deposited to my bank account easily and effortlessly.

The result was: I got a multitude of orders for the vitamins I was selling and just hours later, I also received the payment of my client.

2) FEEL

Living gratitude has taught me I should feel "gratitude or appreciation to unfold the good that I desire."

I have found it very helpful to do a Heart Meditation and feel gratitude for the things I want to demonstrate. I feel the feeling of gratitude as if what I am praying for has already demonstrated.

It's incredible what this metaphysical practice of feeling gratitude can do. We all know that there are moments in our lives when

our relationships can get tested. And I experienced this with my family. Since I am very metaphysical in my approach to life, this has caused some difficulty in relating to my family members who are very pragmatic. Before I moved out of the house, my family would constantly tell me, prayer is not the only way to solve a problem. You also have to take physical action.

And while what they are saying is definitely correct. I go with systematically praying, meditating and "feeling" the answered prayer first before I take "inspired action"

and not just any action to solve any issue in my life. In my years of experience, the situations in my life where I used my Divine Intuition (this inner nudge after I pray or meditate) as the source of my inspired action,

I was always led to solutions that brought greater good to myself and everyone around me. It made me realize,

life doesn't give us solutions wherein you need to compromise. It taught me that one should really expand one's consciousness and alignment to Source Energy for the most benevolent outcome as Tom T. Moore says in the book *The Gentle Way*.

3) SAY

In Dr. Catherine Ponder's (world-renowned prosperity and healing author) writings, she says "The word utter and outer have the same root meaning." what we want to demonstrate in our life experience

we should use the power of affirmations or the words we speak to make firm the good we want to manifest.

And one of my favorite affirmations from her Prosperity Decrees is this:

"I now move forward to my expanded good, divinely directed and lavishly prospered. All things conform to the right thing for me now quickly, easily and in peace."

I used this affirmation in order to move out of our family home. And the result was, I was able to move out of our family home into a space that closely resembles the space I put in my goals book.

There was a time in my life when I did not know the power of words or the things I say to create a new reality for me. I had to work very hard for them back then. Now I just use the simple yet powerful metaphysical tools like the power of words to demonstrate what I want in my life. Then I realize now, the money, the opportunities and the right people come into play to demonstrate my desires.

4) DO

Living gratitude has taught me doing the best I can with what I have will unfold my good.

And my personal opinion is this, tithing time, talent and treasure is an important part of "doing" to unfold one's desired good.

Through prayer, meditation and spiritual studies, one is able to accomplish the action steps that set a good foundation to unfold one's good. I always start and end my day by reading a metaphysical literature, affirmative prayers and meditation to start and end my day.

This habit has helped me perform the work I do with love and joy so I can give my best to the people around me. And the amazing thing is this, I noticed that by giving my best at work

I also receive the fullness of that joyful giving in service.

Either I receive people's heartfelt thank you's or I get lots of delightful expected and unexpected outcomes.

Another powerful action one can take is tithing one's talent or service.

I learned from Stretton Smith's class, if you can tithe your service to the source of your spiritual help and nourishment, you are making yourself magnetic to the good you desire.

Opportunities open up for you. Tithing one's service can something be as simple as sharing Facebook posts of University of Metaphysics or the spiritual organization you are part of.

I know someone who love-fully devoted her service and time to her spiritual organization. She has four children and did not have enough money to send her children to school. But her tithing of talent made her attractive to two generous relatives who sent her children to school joyfully.

Now all her four children are done with college and are now making her life easy and graceful.

And last but one of the most important action or "doing" to live gratitude is tithing one's money or returning 10% of one's income to the source of one's spiritual help and nourishment.

If one takes action by taking definite financial acknowledgement that God is the Source of one's supply one will be delighted to see that most of his or her desires come to pass in ease and grace or something better unfolds.

I started tithing my treasure or money when it seemed impractical to do so.

But I am so grateful that this secret of acknowledging God as one's source of supply (by returning one's 10% to the source of one's spiritual help and nourishment) has helped me put a lot of the things I needed to put in order gracefully.

It has helped me fulfill some of the things I needed to pay. I also noticed that the remaining money I have go further than I can imagine. How? Sometimes, after tithing money, and I'm about to buy food a friend would offer to pay for my bill.

About Reg Tan

Reverend Reg Tan is a life coach, metaphysician and energy healer and a talk show host for "Goals with Reverend Reg" at Facebook channel, WowVeryGood-Live. She's been in the field of wellness for several years now working with industry leaders and some college students both in and out of the Philippines. Her clients are in the field of entertainment, film, sports, business and education. Over the years she has helped people transform their limited lives to a dynamic state of growth, change, and expansion. She believes that the slight shift in consciousness can actually spell the difference between an average life to that of optimal living. She currently studies with University of Metaphysics, Fit College, and Precision Nutrition.